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THE NEXUS BETWEEN REVENUES, REAL FOREIGN EXCHANGE RATES AND AUTOMOTIVE INDUSTRY EXPORTS: THE CASE OF TURKEY, MEXICO, AND GERMANY

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ABSTRACT

The aim of this study is to examine the effect of importing country's revenue (GDP per capita) and the relative exchange rate between the importing country and the exporting country on the automotive exports of Turkey, Mexico and Germany. For this purpose, three separate models were fitted for each country and the empirical results reveal that the impact of revenue and real exchange rates on the amount of automotive exports were not statistically significant for Mexico. For Turkey, it has been determined that the revenue of the importing country has a positive effect on Turkey's automotive exports, on the other hand, exchange rates have a negative effect as expected. For Germany, the revenues variable had a statistically significant positive impact, whereas the impact of real exchange rates was statistically significant and negative. Depending on this result, it can be stated that an increase in the incomes of the importing countries will positively affect the automotive exports of Turkey and Germany. On the other hand, it can be stated that a competitive exchange rate is important for the automotive exports of these countries.

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1. Introduction

There are still some debates on the implementation of further policies to increase the amount of GDP for sustainable economic growth, though many economists widely adopt that the amount of exports is one of the most crucial indicators of economic growth in the existing literature. Specifically, many prior research (Agrawal, 2015; Ajmi, Aye, Balcilar, & Gupta, 2015; Balassa, 1978; Emery, 1967; Kalaitzi & Cleeve, 2018; Mahmoodi & Mahmoodi, 2016; Medina-Smith, 2001; Michaely, 1977; Sunde, 2017) puts forward that the amount of exports has a statistically significant impact on economic growth of selected countries. On the one hand, the amount of exports is considered to the level of production by increasing a country's demand on products. On the other hand, the amount of exports provides a potential increase on the amount of total productivity with a transition is achieved from import substitution sectors, where production factors are not efficiently used, to export industries where production factors are intensively used (Tsen, 2010).

Earlier studies that concentrate on determining factors influencing the amount of exports appear to be limited. Particularly, Sharma (2000) investigates potential determinants of exports in India during the sample period 1970-1998 using time series analysis. In the underlying study, export capacity index was selected as the dependent variable, while GDP, relative export price index, and real foreign exchange rate of India were considered as independent variables. As expected, a 10% increase on real exchange rate was found to have a 3.6% increase on export volume index whereas a 10% increase on export prices of India was found to have an almost 11% decrease on export volume index. The impact of GDP on export volume index was not found as statistically significant. On the other hand, Majeed, Ahmad, and Khawaja (2006) have carried out a comprehensive panel data analysis on 75 developing countries during the sample period 1970-2004 to determine potential factors affecting exports. Their results indicate that GDP and real foreign exchange rate have a statistically significant positive impact on the amount of exports. A similar research on 24 developing countries was conducted by Mehrara, Seijani, and Karsalari (2017) for the sample period 1996-2013 using panel data analyzes. Their results reveal that corporate structure and human capital have a statistically

significant increasing impact on advanced technology exports. However, foreign exchange rates, population, foreign direct investments, and inflation rate were not found to have a statistically significant impact on exports.

Foreign exchange rates and revenues are two prominent factors that may possibly influence the amount of exports. Particularly, an increase in foreign exchange rates for a country principally leads to reduce the amount of imports for that country. Similarly, an increase in income levels for an importer country may lead to an increase on consumption levels. The increasing amount of consumption is usually compensated from both domestic products and foreign products with respect to the marginal import propensity. In this circumstance, the amount of exports tends to increase for the exporter country. It is also crucial for exporter countries to concentrate on most appropriate industries in order to boost their amount of exports. Along with the wave of globalization, many multinational companies have transferred several phases of their production process into developing countries due to a variety of reasons including relatively low wages of labor force and less rigorous environmental standards. This situation enables both the transfer of advanced technology and an increase on production and employment levels by the courtesy of increasing investments for developing countries (Alfaro et al. 2004; Durham, 2004; Iamsiraroj, 2016; Sothan, 2017). The transfer of production process to developing countries is also frequently experienced in the automotive industry that provides multinational companies several advantages such as reduced costs and efficient production close to the market.

The transfer of production process makes a significant contribution to developing economies. Not surprisingly, the relatively high demand in the automotive industry provides to increase in the amount of exports and industrial products usually dominate the export structure. Additionally, these investments in developing countries facilitate to allocate financial support to import their investment goods. Turkey and Mexico are considered as two important developing countries in terms of automotive industry as they are considered as crucial production points for international automotive companies which purpose to establish exports to European and the North American markets. However, both countries use relatively high amount of imported inputs despite their successes on export performance in the automotive industry. Among others, Germany plays a crucial role in the automotive industry using less amount of imported inputs. In that sense, any future attempt to examine German economy along with

Turkish and Mexican counterparts would also provide to seek the impact of imported inputs. Therefore, the present study examines the impact of revenues and foreign exchange rates of importer countries on the exports of automotive industry is separately investigated for Turkish, Mexican, and German economies.

2. The current situation of Turkey, Mexico, and Germany in the automotive industry

The automotive industry has an important place for foreign trade and Germany comes into prominence as a leading country in the underlying industry with the highest numbers of both production and exports though the transfer of a variety of production process into developing countries. Particularly, Germany's exports in the automotive industry have reached to more than \$250 billion in 2017, nearly doubles the automotive industry exports of second-placed country, Japan. Mexico takes the fourth place among the exporter countries in the automotive industry with more than \$100 billion, while Turkey takes the 13th place with \$23 billion (United Nations, 2019).

The 1996 Customs Union Agreement with the European Union was considered to have a significant impact on the Turkish exports in the automotive industry. The Turkish exports in the automotive industry have an increasing trend especially since 2000 until the 2008 Global Economic Crisis. Particularly, the Turkish economy has experienced the unfavorable effects of significant decline on automotive industry exports until 2016 since Turkish exports in the automotive industry are mainly made to the European Union member states. Along with the Customs Union Agreement, many international companies have transferred their production process to the Turkish market in order to take the advantages of extended European market and lower wages in Turkey that makes the country as one of the most important production centers for the European market (Akbulut, 2007; Hüseyini et al. 2017)

Mexico has been emerged as one of the most important production points for the North American market as well where the number of Mexican exports in the automotive industry have a steadily increasing trend. The automotive industry exports in Mexico have recorded a significant increase especially since 1990s and a stronger increasing trend was achieved after 2000s. However, the Mexican economy has also suffered from the 2008 Global Economic Crisis, while the Mexican economy has rapidly recovered the significant

decline in 2009 and the automotive industry exports in 2010 have even exceeded the number of exports in 2008. Not surprisingly, North and South American countries appear to be the most important importers of the Mexican economy in the automotive industry and the country is also considered as a crucial production center for sales in the North and South America for many international companies (United Nations, 2019).

Germany has reached to more than \$250 billion of automotive industry exports in the late of 2017 which even exceeds the total exports of many countries. The amount of exports in the automotive industry has an increasing trend since 1990 for Germany until a slight decline in 1993. However, the exports in the automotive industry for Germany have also been suffered from the negative effects of the 2008 Global Economic Crisis, where the underlying exports have dramatically fallen from \$230 billion to \$155 billion between 2008 and 2009. The recovery period has started since 2011 and the exports in the automotive industry for Germany have successfully caught the numbers of pre-crisis period. However, a stable period has been experienced between 2011 and 2017 in terms of exports in the automotive industry. Apart from Turkish and Mexican exports, there is no clear regional cluster for German exports in the automotive industry.

3. The data and econometric model

This study aims to investigate the impact of foreign exchange rate and importer country revenues on the amount of exports in the automotive industry of Turkey, Mexico, and Germany separately for the sample period 1996-2016. For this purpose, the fitted model can be defined as the following by taking the natural logarithms of all variables:

$$EXV_{it} = GDP_{it} + REER_{it} + u_{it} \quad (1)$$

In Equation (1), EXV_{it} denotes the amount of exports in the automotive industry for selected countries to country i in time period t ; GDP_{it} denotes the amount of GDP per capita in current US dollars for importer country i in time period t ; and finally $REER_{it}$ denotes the

ratio of real foreign exchange rates for selected importer and exporter countries.

The amount of exports in the automotive industry was considered as the dependent variable separately for Turkey, Mexico, and Germany. This variable comprises all countries within the availability of the data between 1996 and 2016. In Equation (1), GDP variable is expected to have a positive sign since an increase on the amount of GDP for country i leads to an increase on purchasing power and consequently an increase on the amount of imports from the exporter country. On the other hand, a potential increase on nominal foreign exchange rate in a country leads to an increase on prices of imported goods and the amount of imports tends to decrease for the corresponding country. Consequently, in case of utilizing from nominal foreign exchange rate, the sign of this variable is expected to be negative. However, if the inflation rate increase exceeds the increase on nominal foreign exchange rate for a country, the increase on the prices of domestic goods exceeds the prices of imported goods. In that case, the amount of imports in the corresponding country tends to increase and the amount of exports for selected exporter countries also tends to increase. Due to the aforementioned deficiency, the use of nominal foreign exchange rate may lead to obtain unexpected sign. Therefore, the use of real foreign exchange rate may provide to overcome such an issue as real foreign exchange rate calculation also considers the inflation rates. When the real foreign exchange rate index increases, the prices of imported goods decrease and this variable is expected to have a positive sign. The use of only opponent country's real foreign exchange rate may pose some deficiencies. When the real foreign exchange rate in a country increases (i.e. the import cheapens), this country tends to increase its imports. However, if the currency in an exporter country appreciates (decline of nominal exchange rates), exporters tend to increase their prices in foreign currency. In such a situation, the products purchased from exporter country will be relatively expensive. Consequently, the use of only opponent country's real foreign exchange rate may avoid to determine the actual impact of the real foreign exchange rate. In this study, the exporter country's (i.e. Mexico, Turkey, and Germany) real foreign exchange rate was divided by importer country's real foreign exchange rate and incorporated in the fitted models in order to overcome such deficiencies. This variable is expected to have a negative sign. Except for the real foreign exchange rate for Turkey, all data were drawn from The World Bank (2018) and the real foreign exchange

rate for Turkey is drawn from Federal Reserve Bank of St. Louis (2018).

In panel data analysis, it is crucial to ensure the stationary condition of variables as spurious regression issue may arise for fitted models with nonstationary variables. The relevant stationary tests are commonly determined with respect to cross section dependence condition of selected variables. Specifically, first generation unit root tests such as Im, Pesaran, and Shin (2003), Levin, Lin, and Chu (2002) are generally used when there is no serious cross section dependence in panel data. However, the evidence gathered from first generation unit root tests may be biased in the presence of cross-sectional dependence. In such a situation, second generation unit root tests such as Hadri and Kurozumi (2012) and Pesaran (2007) are frequently recommended. In order to observe cross section dependence in panel data, the LM test, proposed by Breusch and Pagan (1980), can be used. However, the LM test may produce biased results when cross section dimension (N) is greater than time dimension (T) of the panel ($N > T$). Pesaran, Ullah, and Yamagata (2008) proposed an adjusted $CDLM_{adj}$ test statistic by adding the variance and the mean to the standard LM test statistic. The standard LM test statistic can be defined as

$$LM = T \sum_{i=j}^{n-1} \sum_{j=i+1}^n \rho_{ij}^2 \quad (2)$$

where ρ_{ij}^2 denotes bilateral correlation among error series such like

$$\rho_{ij} = \rho_{ji} = \frac{\sum_{t=1}^T e_{it} e_{jt}}{\left(\sum_{t=1}^T e_{it}^2 \right)^{1/2} \left(\sum_{j=1}^T e_{jt}^2 \right)^{1/2}} \quad (3)$$

In Equation (3), e_{it} denotes error series obtained from each unit by ordinary least squares for T observations and $i = 1, \dots, N$. Furthermore, the bias-adjusted LM test statistic, proposed by

Pesaran, et al. (2008), by adding the mean μ_{Tij} and variance u_{Tij} of the units, is described as the following:

$$LM_{adj} = NLM^{**} = \sqrt{\frac{2T}{N(N-1)}} \left(\sum_{i=j}^{n-1} \sum_{j=i+1}^n \frac{(T-K)\rho_{ij}^2 - \mu_{Tij}}{u_{Tij}} \right) \quad (4)$$

The test statistics obtained from Equation (4) shows normal distribution asymptotically and the alternative hypothesis proposes the presence of the cross-section dependence among units. When the probability value gathered from the underlying test is less than 0.05 at 5% significance level, the alternative hypothesis is not rejected that implies the presence of cross section dependence among series (Pesaran, et al., 2008).

4. Empirical findings

In this study, the presence of cross section dependence among variables and cointegration equations are examined using bias-adjusted LM test. Table 1 presents cross section dependence test results. For brevity, the presence of cross section dependence is simultaneously presented with estimation results.

Table 1. Cross section dependence test results bias-adjusted LM

Variable	Turkey		Mexico		Germany	
	Statistic Value	Prob.	Statistic Value	Prob.	Statistic Value	Prob.
EXV	159,38	0.000	145,85	0.000	240,58	0.000
GDP	201,58	0.000	120,53	0.000	345,51	0.000
REER	53,18	0.000	220,6	0.000	245,21	0.000

As shown in Table 1, the probability values of selected variables for all three countries are less than 0.05 at 5% significance level that implies the presence of cross section dependence among variables. Therefore, the stationarity conditions of variables were investigated using CADF unit root test, as shown in Table 2.

Table 2. CADF unit root test results

	Variable	Level			First Difference			Critical Value 1%	
		Trend	Lag	Statistic	Trend	Lag	Statistic		
Turkey	EXV	1	5	-2,76	1	4	-3,35	Only intercept	-2,25
	GDP	1	3	-2,51	1	3	-2,85		
	REER	0	5	-1,91	0	5	-2,73	Intercept & Trend	-2,76
Mexico	EXV	1	4	-2,15	1	4	-3,41	Only intercept	-2,32
	GDP	1	4	-2,12	1	4	-2,93		
	REER	0	4	-1,5	0	4	-2,56	Intercept & Trend	-2,83
Germany	EXV	1	1	-2,35	1	1	-3,02	Only intercept	-2,20
	GDP	1	2	-2,42	1	2	-2,96		
	REER	0	4	-1,82	0	4	-2,49	Intercept & Trend	-2,72

In CADF unit root test, calculated test statistics are compared with critical values by considering both time and cross section dimensions. When absolute values of calculated test statistics are greater than one can argue that selected variables are stationary. As shown in Table 2, calculated test statistics for all variables are less than critical values implying that these variables are not stationary at their levels. On the other hand, all variables were found as stationary at the first difference. After ensuring the stationarity of variables at the first difference level, cointegration conditions of selected variables are sought and long-term coefficients were calculated using CCEMG estimator (Westerlund, 2008).

Table 3. Estimation results

Dependent Variable: EXV						
	Mexico		Turkey		Germany	
	I	II	III	IV	V	VI
GDP	0.42 (1.15)	0.74 (1.77)	1.15** (0.34)	2.91** (1.15)	1.06** (0.30)	2.18** (0.41)
REER		0.46 (6.89)		-3.91* (2.93)		-2.60** (0.95)
LM_{adj}	47.66 [0.000]	26.79 [0.000]	156.27 [0.000]	88.76 [0.000]	47.06 [0.000]	223.36 [0.000]

() denotes standard error; [] denotes probability; *statistically significant at 10% significance level **statistically significant at 1% significance level

As seen in Table 3, revenues were not found as a statistically significant variable on the automotive industry exports of Mexico in Model I. When the foreign exchange rate variable was included in Model II, none of revenues and foreign exchange rate variables were found as statistically significant. This evidence can be explained by the dominance of automotive industry exports for Mexico to the US, while three quarters of Mexican automotive industry exports are made to the US. Whilst these models were estimated using the datasets of 33 countries, the actual impact of other importer countries was not observed. The empirical evidence of Model III for Turkey revealed that revenues have a statistically significant positive impact on Turkish automotive industry exports implying that when revenues of importer countries increase, the amount of automotive industry exports to the underlying countries tend to increase in line with economic theory. When the real foreign exchange rate variable was included in Model IV, both GDP and real foreign exchange rate were found as statistically significant with expected signs. The empirical evidence gathered from Model V and Model VI for Germany indicates that both GDP and foreign exchange rate variables were statistically significant with expected signs. Particularly, when revenues of importer countries increase, the amount of German automotive industry exports to the underlying countries tend to increase. On the other hand, in case of a relatively decrease on real foreign exchange rate of Germany, the amount of automotive industry exports tends to increase.

When all empirical evidence of this study is simultaneously considered, GDP of opponent country has a statistically significant impact on automotive industry exports for selected countries. The impact of foreign exchange rate was found as insignificant for Mexico, while this impact was significant but weak for Turkey. This evidence can be associated with the imported inputs as both Turkey and Mexico are highly dependent on imported inputs in the production process. Though an increase on foreign exchange rates may also expected to an increase on the competitive power of exporters, foreign exchange rate increases lead to increasing production costs. The empirical evidence gathered from German case may in line with this interpretation. In German case, the imported inputs are relatively low than Mexico and Turkey and thus, the impact of real foreign exchange rate was found as statistically significant.

5. Conclusion

The welfare level increase is considered as one of the most important goals of underdeveloped and developing countries. The underlying countries especially concentrate on relevant policies that facilitate to increase their GDP levels. Particularly, the amount of exports is commonly adopted as a crucial determinant to contribute to increasing GDP. On the other hand, countries should emphasize on proper industries to boost their amount of exports. Along with rapid developments in transportation and communication technologies, many countries are able to transfer their production process into different countries in the automotive industry especially after 1980s. Under the great export potential of automotive industry, production process transfer facilitates a significant change on the structure of exports and foreign exchange reserves for many developing countries. By courtesy of production transfer, these developing countries have the opportunity to import more investment goods and a more sustainable economic growth. In that sense, any attempt that concentrate to examine potential determinants of automotive industry exports provide valuable information for future economic policies.

This study investigates the impact of GDP and foreign exchange rates on the amount of automotive industry exports for three selected countries, namely, Turkey, Mexico, and Germany using panel data models. The empirical evidence of this study revealed that GDP and foreign exchange rates were not statistically significant on the

amount of automotive industry exports for Mexican case. In German and Turkish cases, both GDP and foreign exchange rates were found to have a statistically significant impact on the amount of automotive exports, though the impact of foreign exchange rate was relatively weak for Turkish case. This evidence is in line with some previous research (Balcilar, Bal, Algan, & Demiral, 2014) in the existing literature, whereas contradicts with some others (Sharma, 2000). The impact of real foreign exchange rate was found to have a statistically significant impact on the amount of automotive industry exports for both Germany and Turkey, but this impact was relatively weak for Turkey. So, the impact of foreign exchange rate on the amount of automotive industry exports deserves further investigation. In that context, this result shows contradiction with previous research (Balcilar, et al., 2014).

The impact of GDP on the amount of automotive industry exports for Germany can be associated with the widespread structure of automotive industry exports of Germany. In fact, the automotive industry exports in Germany are not clustered in a certain country group. The crucial role of imported inputs for Turkish and Mexican cases can be considered as the reason of not reflecting the actual impact of real foreign exchange rates on the amount of automotive industry exports for such cases. By courtesy of relatively low dependency on imported inputs for German case, the impact of real foreign exchange rate was found to be statistically significant variable on the amount of automotive industry exports. Developing countries like Turkey and Mexico should concentrate on further policies that encourage the differentiation of exporting countries to increase their automotive industry exports caused by GDP increases. Additionally, foreign exchange rates are important policy instruments on the balance of payments. In case of any deficit, central banks may encourage to increase real foreign exchange rates to overcome such deficits. However, further policies should also pay special attention on decreasing the dependency of imported inputs especially in automotive industry in order to sustain the efficiency of foreign exchange rate policies.

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